

Hierarchical exploration of artworks through 2-DOF haptic device: a usability study

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Abstract. To make museums accessible to blind and partially blind visitors, we developed a haptic system prototype, named Force Feedback Tablet (F2T), allowing a hierarchical exploration presentation composed of three different exploration modes: global guidance, detailed guidance, and without guidance. These modes support synchronized audio-haptic feedback. To test this presentation on the proposed device, a usability test has been done using two scenes from the Tapestry of the Apocalypse in the Castle of Angers (France). Subsequently, user feedback was collected through Likert scale ratings and open-ended questions. The results are presented and discussed. In this study, participants generally appreciated the guidance modes, particularly for their ability to identify important objects in a scene.

Keywords: blindness · multisensory integration · artworks · force-feedback.

1 Introduction

While a substantial body of literature has explored multisensory integration, particularly through audio-haptic modalities, not enough attention is paid to the accessibility of 2D artworks. This gap is evident in reviews of accessibility for blind and partially sighted (BPS) individuals, where the predominant solutions rely on 2.5D replicas [3]. To that extent, the Force Feedback Tablet (F2T), a 2-DOF haptic prototype, is used. In previous works [1,2], the F2T design was presented and a methodology was proposed; however, no studies were conducted with the device using images of artworks with the targeted audience. Our work aims to investigate how audio-haptic feedback through a hierarchical exploration presentation influences the user exploration experience of the Tapestry of the Apocalypse among BPS and sighted individuals.

2 System design

The F2T is a haptic device featuring a flat-headed joystick movable on a 2D plane [1]. It is connected to a Java Interface displaying virtual images on a computer.

Certain regions of the image are marked as "*areas of interest*" providing notable haptic feedback when explored. The F2T renders friction and height illusion through kinesthetic feedback. These effects are managed by a dedicated class for virtual images, with each pixel's RGB channels representing distinct properties. Additional classes handle effects such as flows and rails, encoding vector fields via the red and green channels in each pixel.

3 Experiment

Ten participants (3 sighted, 7 BPS people; aged 41 to 77; 4 females, 6 males) were recruited with ethical clearance. This experiment was part of a bigger experiment with tests on multiple devices, thus to avoid bias we selected scenes that were not viewed nor tested by participants. Two images from the Tapestry of the Apocalypse were used for a usability study to avoid bias. One group explored scene 1 (S1) with 2 sighted and 3 BPS participants, while scene 2 (S2) was explored by 1 sighted and 4 BPS participants.

Fig. 1. Experiment procedure of a hierarchical exploration with F2T

Figure 1 shows the experimental procedure to test the hierarchical exploration presentation [2]. In the global guidance mode, participants traced, with the joystick, manually annotated paths synchronized with audio descriptions. Detailed guidance mode comprises two stages: find and select an object in the scene with the help of attractive forces and audio feedback areas, then passively follow objects' shapes with synchronized audio descriptions. In each scene, the exploration without guidance features audio feedback areas, with verbal descriptions and sound effects, and four haptic effects to enhance its semantic value: fluid friction, solid friction, wall, and flow effects. Friction coefficients were optimized for minimal input effort from participants to perceive resistive forces. Wall effects restricted exploration in the scene frame, while flow effects, which are manually applied vector fields, simulated the movement of objects (e.g., (S1) horse galloping and (S2) river flow), thus guiding the joystick when inside.

4 Results, Conclusion and Future work

Participants were given a list of statements (table 1) for the Likert scale, as well as open-answer questions, for each tested method.

Table 1. Statements from the questionnaire used for the Likert Scale.

Questions	Statements
Q1	I appreciated the exploration method
Q2	The amount of audio information is enough
Q3	The amount of information perceived tactily is enough
Q4	Audio and touch integrate well together
Q5	I found the haptic feedback interesting.
Q6	I understood the scene presented with this method of exploration
Q7	This method of exploration was sufficient to understand the scene
Q8	The exploration methods were repetitive
Q9	I felt different haptic feedback

The global guidance mode received higher appreciation from participants than the detailed guidance mode and the exploration without guidance. Some participants noted that this method provides objects' dimensions and relative sizes compared to other objects in the scene. However, opinions were mixed regarding the perception of tactile information provided by the guided exploration modes. Some BPS participants were pleasantly surprised to perceive the contours in detail in the detailed guidance mode. Three participants mentioned the need for sound signals to distinguish objects from one another. Another three participants remarked that the global and detailed guidance modes were complementary. In the exploration without guidance mode, participants felt that the flow and attraction effects were more prominent compared to friction effects. Participants gave positive reviews for the synchronous fusion of verbal descriptions and haptic feedback, as both modalities enhanced the exploration. The exploration without guidance mode required more explanation of the haptic effects, indicating that a learning phase would be necessary for future tests.

In conclusion, participants of this usability test valued the guidance modes in the hierarchical exploration presentation. The exploration modes were varied and complementary, facilitating independent exploration of 2D artworks by BPS museum visitors. However, several limitations should be noted. The sample size for each scene needs to be larger, and further research is required to integrate various haptic effects based on semantic objects for exploration without guidance.

Future work could explore using saliency-driven data to modulate haptic feedback, and on-site testing in front of the Tapestry to gather more comprehensive data.

Acknowledgments. We would like to express our gratitude to all participants involved in our study, as well as to the Castle of Angers for their hospitality. This study was funded by the ANR IMG Project (ANR-20-CE38-0007) and a grant from Dassault Systems La Fondation.

Disclosure of Interests. The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article. Our research Laboratory, LITIS, has received research grants from Dassault Fondation for the development of our haptic tablet.

References

1. Gay, S.L., Pissaloux, E., Romeo, K., Truong, N.T.: F2t: A novel force-feedback haptic architecture delivering 2d data to visually impaired people. *IEEE Access* **9** (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3091441>
2. Pissaloux, E., Djoussouf, L., Romeo, K., Ramiro, V., Gay, S.L., Truong, N.T., Dao, S.D.: A new approach to assist virtual image accessibility for visually impaired people. In: *Universal Access in HCI. User and Context Diversity*, vol. 13309, pp. 251–261. Springer Inter. Publishing (2022). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-05039-8_18
3. Sylaiou, S., Fidas, C.: Supporting people with visual impairments in cultural heritage: Survey and future research directions. *Inter. Journal of HCI* pp. 1–16 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1080/10447318.2022.2098930>, publisher: Taylor & Francis